

PERFORMANCE BASIS FOR THE APPLICATIONS
OF ARAMID FIBER REINFORCEMENT

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I. Introduction

Until the advent of high strength (525×10^3 psi, 3620 MN/m^2), high modulus (9 to 19×10^6 psi, 62 to 131 GN/m^2), organic fibers (0.053 lb/in^3 , 1.45 g/cm^3) such as Kevlar® aramid, the reinforcement of plastics had been the almost exclusive domain of inorganic fibers, primarily glass. Concurrently, rubber reinforcement has benefited over the years with ever-improving organic fibers beginning with cotton, then rayon, nylon, and polyester; but with inorganics such as glass fiber and steel wire more recently penetrating these uses.

Glass fiber, driven by the variety of values it offers as a reinforcement, and its inherent textile and insulation assets, has developed in the last 30 years into a billion pound market that has allowed for attractive pricing (Ref. 1). Boron and graphite fibers, on the other hand, developed in the late 1950's to meet the need for greater specific modulus than achievable with glass (Ref. 2), have grown to a business in the hundreds of thousands of pounds propelled by a more restricted functionality based on high strength and modulus per unit weight.

However, strength and stiffness alone is rarely what is sought in the reinforcement of either plastics or rubber, and the purpose of this paper will be to review the unique combinations of properties of this general class of high performance aramid fibers as they relate to their broad present and projected usage.

II. Fiber Types and Properties

"Kevlar" is available in three types: "Kevlar", "Kevlar" 29 and "Kevlar" 49 intended primarily for rubber reinforcement, special industrial uses and plastics reinforcement, respectively, Fig. 1. "Kevlar" was designed specifically for tire and rubber reinforcement, while "Kevlar" 29 is made available in forms particularly suited for its specialty uses. The "Kevlar" family is twice as strong, and an order of magnitude higher in modulus, than nylon. This makes them similar to glass fibers in stiffness. "Kevlar" 49 combines the strength of "Kevlar" 29 with a modulus twice that of glass fiber or two-thirds that of steel wire.

These properties are coupled with the low density (1.44-1.45 g/cc), non-conductivity and textile processibility inherent to their organic nature. Their temperature stability and chemical resistance allow processing not only according to methods developed for other industrial organics like nylon or polyester, but also by those of the glass fiber industry. Their very low creep and excellent creep rupture characteristics allow these aramids to be loaded to high percentages of their ultimate strength for prolonged periods without time induced failures (Ref. 3 and 4).

III. Fiber Forms and Processing

High strength and modulus aramid products are available commercially in the form of yarns, rovings and woven fabrics of various descriptions; and in developmental quantities of nonwoven fabrics, insulation batts and chopped fibers (Ref. 5). These products can, in turn, be handled as industrial textiles, with the attention that their high modulus and relatively low elongation-to-break requires, or preimpregnated, wet layed-up, filament-wound, pultruded, press cured, vacuum bagged, autoclave cured, etc., as their glass fiber counterparts. Machining requires special care if aesthetics of the cut surfaces are important, and guidelines have been developed to accomplish this (Ref. 6). Precaution should be taken to protect "Kevlar" items from degradation due to prolonged exposure to UV radiation. Self-screening will take place in items of substantial cross-section, and where this is not practical, appropriate jacketing or laminating for effective UV screening can be recommended (Ref. 6). Finally, care should be taken to select "Kevlar" with the appropriate cordage finish for significantly enhanced durability in applications such as ropes and cables where severe abrasion is anticipated.

IV. Major End Uses

In what follows we will describe the performance characteristics of reinforcing aramid fibers as they relate to the end-use requirements of the major markets in which they are competing. To do this concisely, the reader will frequently be referred to

references where technical claims are documented more fully. The list of references provides a reasonably complete bibliography of recent applications of "Kevlar" aramid fibers disclosed in the literature.

Tires

Substantial penetration of the tire market is expected for "Kevlar". Du Pont data on Du Pont-made tires indicate that from a durability, ride, and hazard resistance point of view, "Kevlar" outperforms steel wire in the belts of radial tires at significant belt weight savings (Fig. 2). Based on performance and economics at the time of this writing, five "Kevlar" belted passenger tire lines had been announced in the U.S.A. and one in Europe, and additional lines were expected. Light and heavy truck, and off-the-road vehicle tires, are also under active development.

Mechanical Rubber Goods

"Kevlar" offers a unique balance of properties for the reinforcement of rubber in the hose and belting markets. The primary limitations of incumbent fibers that "Kevlar" overcomes are shown in Fig. 3 together with "Kevlar" products that already have been commercialized. These aramid products are expected to offer considerable advantage in automotive radiator and heater hoses with temperature capabilities up to 300°F. Use of "Kevlar" has been reported (Ref. 7) in anhydrous ammonia hose with high burst, low volumetric expansion and superior chemical resistance than incumbent products; and in high pressure hose which is non-conductive and more flexible than their steel reinforced counterparts.

Ropes and Cables

Organic fibers such as nylon or Dacron® polyester have long been used successfully in the soft cordage markets; but, their properties limit their ability to perform in applications requiring high strength and low stretch such as wire ropes and electro-mechanical cables. "Kevlar" 29 and "Kevlar" 49 fibers with their high strength and modulus approaching that of steel, combined with light weight, not only can compete with wire in ropes and cables, but permit the realization of systems not practical with steel or other synthetic fibers. Their strength-to-weight ratio is illustrated in the free length "Kevlar" will support in both air and water as compared to steel (Fig. 4). "Kevlar" can offer substantially increased payloads in long cables used in the oceanographic and aerospace markets (Ref. 8 and 9). Additionally, corrosion resistance, non-conductivity, and improved handleability have suggested applications in oil rig, buoy and sonabuoy mooring (Ref. 10), air and sea towed antennas (Ref. 11), helicopter hoist and anchor pendant lines, balloon tethering, antenna guys (Ref. 12), running and standing rigging, etc.

"Kevlar" 29 and "Kevlar" 49 can be used either as "soft yarns" like nylon and "Dacron" on conventional textile twisting, stranding, or braiding equipment, or as resin impregnated strands which may be handled like steel wires on wire stranding, braiding, and cabling equipment. Some comparisons of different types of rope and cable structures made with "Kevlar" and conventional materials are shown in Fig. 5. Note that constructions of the wire rope type: 1x7, 7x7, 7x19, etc., have been made with aramids that have equivalent or better strength than their steel counterparts at one-fifth the weight. Terminations 80-100% efficient have been demonstrated for tension members up to 1" diameter (Ref. 13) and are in early development up to 5" diameter.

Protective

A property that illustrates the versatility of aramid fibers is the ballistic protection they offer in the forms of unimpregnated fabrics and felts as well as in composite form. Twice the ballistic protection of nylon at equal weight, or equivalent performance at half the weight, can be obtained with properly designed "Kevlar" fabrics. Furthermore, equivalent protection to glass fiber composite armor at two-thirds the weight, have been repeatedly demonstrated. Jet engine turbine blade containment rings in the form of unimpregnated or properly engineered composite armor are being developed (Ref. 14). Protective gloves, aprons, helmets, boots, etc., are in various stages of development utilizing the cut and penetration resistance of these high performance aramids.

Aircraft and Marine

The performance advantages that have led to adoption of "Kevlar" 49 instead of glass fiber in the interiors of commercial aircraft have been presented elsewhere (Ref. 15). Exterior components on Lockheed's L-1011 Tristar wide-bodied jet continue logging successful flight time on commercial routes in a NASA-sponsored flight service evaluation program (Ref. 16 and 17). Confidence built in these programs has led to adoption on Sikorsky's entry in the UTTAS helicopter competition for the U. S. Army, and in Northrop's YF-17 lightweight fighter prototype (Ref. 18). Equivalent or better mechanical performance than the incumbent material at substantial weight savings were the driving forces in these applications. Additionally, low radar profile and good impact characteristics have been important in the development of drone components by Teledyne-Ryan (Ref. 19), and hybrid composite jet engine fan blades by General Electric (Ref. 20), respectively. Non-abrasive wear characteristics are driving the adoption of chopped "Kevlar" 49/epoxy for compression molded blade tip rub strips, while impact resistance, combined with light weight, are the reason for qualification in Boeing 747 cargo compartment liners. The anticipated greater fracture toughness of composites reinforced with "Kevlar" 49 or combinations of it with graphite

versus those reinforced with only the more brittle inorganic fiber has been established quantitatively (Ref. 21, 22; Fig. 6). Flammability characteristics that are of paramount importance in these uses exceed present and proposed FAA specifications when precaution is taken to utilize the appropriate flame retardant resins (Ref. 23).

The requirements for improved stiffness with weight economy apply also to the hulls of sailboats. Furthermore, competitive advantages are gained by saving weight above the waterline and redistributing the savings for maximum structural efficiency within the overall fixed weight that may be dictated by class rules. Combinations of "Kevlar" 49 with glass fiber in woven or chopped mat form have been popular in marine applications (Ref. 24, 25). "Kevlar" 29 and "Kevlar" 49 standing and running rigging replacing steel and polyester, respectively, are also gaining acceptance.

Aerospace

The possibilities of "Kevlar" 49 as a superior filament winding fiber for internally pressurized vessels were recognized early (Ref. 26). Pressure vessel performance factors (PV/W) of 1.8×10^6 in. have been obtained routinely in pressure vessels of up to 8" in diameter (Ref. 27), and this performance translated into successful firing of full-size solid propellant rocket motor cases (Ref. 28).

The excellent retention of tensile strength of "Kevlar" 49 at cryogenic temperatures has motivated extensive development work funded by NASA in liquid H₂ and O₂ tankage for the Space Shuttle (Ref. 29). In addition, the lower creep and excellent creep rupture characteristics of "Kevlar" 49 are crucial to its utility as a filament-wound pressure vessel reinforcement (Fig. 7). Its non-Griffith flaw sensitive behavior under long-term loading at high percentages of its ultimate tensile strength allow for higher design allowables which, in turn, defrays some of the price premium over glass. Excellent tension-tension fatigue performance further enhances the cost effectiveness of high performance aramids in these uses.

Sporting Goods

The value that the professional and amateur athlete attaches to materials that offer him a competitive edge, has allowed the commercial penetration of certain segments of the sporting goods market by high performance fibers such as graphite and boron. Weight savings, combined with extra stiffness and impact strength, have been the main driving forces of "Kevlar" in these uses (Fig. 8). Hybrids combining aramid fibers with glass or graphite fiber have been common in these applications. Scarcity of good wood has motivated development of combinations of "Kevlar" 49 in fabric, roving or tape form with lower grade woods to obtain superior

performance. The fabricability of "Kevlar" 49 with the same shop procedures used for glass fiber and its availability in forms that allow a gage-for-gage replacement has accelerated the acceptance of the aramid reinforcement in these uses (Ref. 24).

Coated Fabrics

Fig. 9 shows "Hypalon" coated nylon fabric (5.1 oz/yd²) intended as air support shelter material, compared to a "Kevlar" 29 analog that utilizes fabric of less than half the basis weight (2.1 oz/yd²). The "Kevlar" item is 20% lighter, stronger, and more tear resistant. Based on laboratory experience, it is estimated that one acre of Teflon®-coated "Kevlar" 29 unidirectional fabric would weigh 4500 lbs vs. over 14,000 lbs for the equal strength glass fabric item. Work by Sheldahl-Advanced Products Division in tethered balloons (Ref. 30) has shown that multi-ply laminates of "Kevlar" fabrics offer significant strength-to-weight improvements, are less permeable, and have equal or better abrasion resistance than conventional "Dacron" polyester reinforced counterparts. Skirts for air cushioned vehicles, specialized conveyor belting, inflatable forms for concrete, and arrester webbing for aircraft are examples of uses under development.

Electrical

The electrical properties of "Kevlar" 49 fabrics in a typical flame retardant epoxy resin are seen in Fig. 10 compared to those of glass fabrics in the same resin, and made by the identical method. The aramid composites are characterized by one unit lower dielectric constant, equivalent loss factor, and similar electrical insulation values than those of glass. These properties, combined with adequate high temperature (150°C) durability and excellent creep rupture characteristics, have motivated development of electrical rotor banding tapes. The wear characteristics of aramid fibers has been of interest in the development of insulation wedges for large electrical generating equipment. Electromechanical cables benefit from the high strength and good dielectric properties of "Kevlar" (Ref. 8).

Electronics

Aramids exhibit lower dielectric constant than glass at frequencies of 1 KHz to 10 GeHz. Thus, they outperform the inorganic fiber up to and including the radar transmission range. Lightweight radomes and electromagnetic windows can be made to advantage with "Kevlar" 49. The relative radar transparency of "Kevlar" reinforced plastic articles have suggested its use where low radar profile is important.

Good dielectric properties, coupled with negative thermal expansion coefficient, has been of interest to circuit board

manufacturers who have performed extensive evaluations on the performance of "Kevlar" in both woven and nonwoven forms for rigid, flexible, and multi-layer boards (Fig. 11). The negative thermal expansion is useful in providing dimensional stability to the circuit board by restraining the possible thermal expansion of the resin matrix. Good tear and crease resistance, as well as tolerance of solder temperatures, have stimulated these developments. The weight saving over glass that invariably accrues from the use of aramids is of further value in airborne electronics.

Insulation

Equivalent or better insulation than obtained with glass combined with weight savings of up to 30% have been demonstrated with "Kevlar" insulation batts (Ref. 5). These consist of nonwoven fibrous assemblies lightly impregnated with appropriately flame retardant resins that give them adequate consistency. Flammability characteristics of these aramid fiber products substantially exceeds specifications. Thermal conductivities in solid laminates made with thermoset resins also are lower than their inorganic fiber counterparts (Fig. 12). Aircraft insulation, liquified natural gas containers, and refrigerated truck trailers have been proposed based on this kind of performance.

Corrosion Resistant

A wide variety of fuels, lubricants and solvents have no deleterious effect on "Kevlar" 49 laminates. The specific retention of strength under prolonged exposure to these environments is reported in detail elsewhere (Ref. 31). The relative insensitivity to hydrolytic attack compared to glass fiber composites has motivated definition of the corrosion resistance of "Kevlar" laminates in very strong acids and bases. "Kevlar" 49/polyester laminates have shown superior performance to glass analogs in caustic environments, and "Kevlar" 49/fluorocarbon matrix laminates have shown good resistance to HF environments up to HF concentrations of 48% at room temperature. No advantage over glass has been demonstrated for "Kevlar" 49 laminates in HCl and HNO₃ environments.

Audio

The utility of lightweight sheet structures comprising low basis weight, thin woven and nonwoven "Kevlar" 49 in speaker cones has been explored. The high specific modulus of these resin impregnated and cured composites has resulted in high acoustical output. Increasing concern in removing flammable components from household radio and TV appliances has further accelerated the evaluation of these inherently flame retardant aramid structures in these uses.

V. Conclusion

This paper has attempted to review the multiplicity of values and associated uses of the "Kevlar" family of reinforcing aramid fibers. The uniqueness of some individual, and many combinations, of their properties, suggests a broad functionality that goes beyond that associated only with their high strength and modulus. Acting alone, or in combination with resins, wood, and other fibers, they constitute a crucial ingredient of a new generation of high performance engineering materials available to man.

References

1. Bastone, A. L. and Rolston, J. A., "Applications of Fibrous Glass Reinforcements for Industrial Composites", National Symposium on Fiber Frontiers, Carnegie Institute, June 10, 1974, Washington, D.C.
2. Johnson, W. P., "The Coming of Age of High Strength-High Modulus Reinforcements for Composites", National Symposium on Fiber Frontiers, Carnegie Institute, June 10, 1974, Washington, D.C.
3. Chiao, T. T., et al., "Filament-Wound Kevlar® 49/Epoxy Pressure Vessels", NASA CR-134506, November 9, 1973.
4. Miner, L. H., et al., "Fatigue, Creep and Impact Resistance of Kevlar® 49 Reinforced Composites", Composites Reliability Conference, The American Society for Testing and Materials, Las Vegas, April 15-16, 1974.
5. Sturgeon, D. L. G., et al., "Kevlar® 49 Woven and Nonwoven Fabric Composites - Performance and Applications", 19th National SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, Vol. 19, p. 229-243, April 1974.
6. Kevlar® 49 Data Manual, E. I. du Pont de Nemours & Co., Inc., Textile Fibers Department, "Kevlar" Special Products, Wilmington, Delaware 19898.
7. Rohlffing, R. A., "New High-Strength Reinforcing Fibers", Rubber and Plastics News, July 1, 1974.
8. Bowers, W. E., "High Strength-to-Weight Cable for Deep Ocean Projects", Proceedings of the International Wire and Cable Symposium 1973, Atlantic City, December 1973, p. 279-285.
9. Hightower, J. D., et al., "Development of PRD-49 Composite Tensile Strength Members", American Society of Mechanical Engineers, Ocean Technology Division, Winter Annual Meeting, Detroit, November 11-15, 1973.

References (Cont.)

10. Swenson, R. C., et al., "Design and Construction of Cables for Sensor Systems", *Sea Technology*, October 1973.
11. Ties, T. S., "Submarine Tow Cables", *Depthlines*, ITT-Cable Hydrospace Division, Vol. 2, No. 1, p. 4, February 1974.
12. Scala, E., "High-Strength Filaments for Cables and Lines", American Society for Testing and Materials, Special Technical Publication 521, 1973, p. 390-408.
13. "Terminations of 'Phillystran' Cable", Philadelphia Resins Corp., Montgomeryville, Pennsylvania 18936.
14. Gerstte, J. H., "Analysis of Rotor Fragment Impact on Ballistic Fabric Engine Burst Containment Shields", Symposium on Propulsion System Integration and Engine Integrity, Naval Post-Graduate School, Monterey, California, Sept. 3-6, 1974.
15. Stone, R. H., "Advanced Organic Fibers for L-1011 Interior Structures", National SAMPE Technical Conference, Los Angeles, California, April 10-12, 1972.
16. Paschal, D. R., "The Successful Use of Composites in the L-1011 Tristar Commercial Transport", Symposium on Reinforced Plastics in Aerospace Applications, The Plastics Institute, London, April 5-6, 1973.
17. Wooley, J. H., "Flight Service Evaluation of PRD-49/Epoxy Composite Panels in Wide-Bodied Commercial Transport Aircraft", First Annual Flight Service Report, LR-26580, NASA Contract NAS1-11621, July 1974.
18. Click, H. F., "Applications of Graphite and Aramid Composites on the YF-17 Prototype Fighter", The Sixth National SAMPE Technical Conference, Vol. 6, p. 352-360, October 1974.
19. Dickard, H. E., et al., "Design and Fabrication of an RPV Wing Panel with PRD-49/Epoxy Skins", AFFDL-TR-73-31, March 1973.
20. Wise, C. E., "Turbofan of the Future", *Machine Design*, p. 20-25, August 22, 1974.
21. Beaumont, P. W. R., et al., "Methods for Improving the Impact Resistance of Composite Materials", ASTM Symposium on Foreign Object Impact Behavior of Composites, Philadelphia, Sept. 20, 1973.

References (Cont.)

22. Zweben, C., "Fracture of Kevlar® 49, E-Glass and Graphite Composites", ASTM Symposium on Fracture Mechanics of Composites, Gaithersburg, Maryland, Sept. 25, 1974.
23. Moore, J. W., et al., "High Modulus Organic Fiber Composites in Aircraft Applications", Composites, Vol. 4, No. 1, p. 34-38, January 1973.
24. Sturgeon, D. L. G., et al., "Kevlar® 49 Composites for Sporting Goods and Recreational Equipment", 19th National SAMPE Symposium and Exhibition, Vol. 19, p. 304-319, April 1974.
25. Riewald, P. G., et al., "Kevlar® 49 Hybrid Composites for Commercial and Aerospace Applications", 30th Annual Conference of the SPI, Reinforced Plastics/Composites Institute, February 1974.
26. Hoggatt, J. T., "High Performance Filament Wound Composites for Pressure Vessel Applications", 1971 National SAMPE Technical Conference on Space Shuttle Materials, Huntsville, Ala., October 1971.
27. Hoggatt, J. T., "Thin-Metal Lined PRD-49-III Composite Vessels", NASA CR-134555, January 1974.
28. Wright, O. C., "Development of a High Performance PRD-49-III Filament-Wound Chamber for Trident I (C4) Third Stage", AIAA/SAE 9th Propulsion Conference, Las Vegas, November 5-7, 1973.
29. Chiao, T. T., et al., "Organic Fiber/Epoxy Pressure Vessels", SAMPE Quarterly, Vol. 5, No. 3, p. 17-27, April 1974.
30. Niccum, R. J., et al., "Investigation of Kevlar® Fabric Based Materials for Use with Inflatable Structures", NASA CR-132411, April 1974.
31. Moore, J. W., et al., "Recent Advances in PRD-49 Composites", 1972 National SAMPE Technical Conference, Palo Alto, Calif., October 17-20, 1972.

FIGURE 1

PROPERTIES* OF BARE REINFORCING YARNS

	<u>Nylon</u>	<u>"Kevlar" & "Kevlar" 29</u>	<u>E-Glass**</u>	<u>"Kevlar" 49</u>	<u>Steel</u>
Specific Gravity	1.14	1.44	2.55	1.45	7.86
Tensile Strength (10 ³ psi)	145	400	220	400	285
Tensile Modulus (10 ⁶ psi)	0.8	9	10	19	29
Elongation (%)	18	4	3	2.4	2

*10-inch gage length, bare yarn, 3 tpi added to organics.

**Owens Corning Fiberglas Corp. Publication No. 1-GT-1375-C.

FIGURE 2

DU PONT DATA ON DU PONT TIRES

	<u>PE/Steel</u>	<u>PE/"Kevlar"</u>
<u>DURABILITY</u>		
Belt Weight, lbs	2.4	0.54
Extended DOT Wheel Tests		
High Speed, MPH	100	125
Endurance, % RL/Miles	168/3300	178/3700
Treadwear, Miles		
ARA Severe XHA-1 Route	27,000 NF	28,000 NF
<u>HAZARD RESISTANCE</u>		
Plunger Energy, in.-lbs.	6100	6700
Impact Plunger		
Height to Failure, in.	4.3	5.3
Cobblestone		
Laps to Failure	4100	13,000
Cut Resistance		
Height to Failure, in.	1.8-5.0	1.5-5.0
DOT Performance		
After Tread Cuts to Belts	Failed	Passed
<u>AESTHETICS</u>		
Ride	Base	+
Handling	Base	=
Noise	Base	+

FIGURE 3

COMMERCIAL "KEVLAR" MECHANICAL RUBBER GOODS

End-Use	Replacing	To Overcome Limitations in
Automotive Cooling Hose Truck/Bus Cooling Hose	Rayon	Heat Degradation Strength
Off-Shore Drilling Hose Automotive & Agricultural V-Belts	Polyester	Heat Degradation Thermal Dimensional Stability
Snowmobile Drive Belts Timing Belts	Glass	Fatigue Life Impact Loading
Anhydrous Ammonia Transfer Hose Miniature Power Transmission	Steel	Weight, Fatigue Life Flexibility, Rust

FIGURE 4

"FREE" LENGTH COMPARISON

(Length at which Strength Member breaks of its own weight = Tensile Strength/Density)

FIGURE 5

STRENGTH OF VARIOUS "KEVLAR" ROPES AND CABLES

<u>Material</u>	<u>Break Dia. (in.)</u>	<u>Str. (lbs)</u>	<u>Weight lb/100 ft</u>	<u>Elong. %</u>	<u>Strength Conversion* %</u>
<u>3-STRAND ROPE</u>					
"Kevlar" 29	0.5	14300	8.1	16	30
"Dacron" T-67	"	6400	8.0	28	29
Nylon T-707	"	7100	6.6	40	36
<u>PARALLEL LAY</u>					
"Kevlar" 29 ("Parafil")	0.28	3650	2.5	2.6	83
"Kevlar" 49 ("Parafil")	"	3320	2.5	1.8	75
Polyester ("Parafil")	"	1700	2.4	7.0	84
"Kevlar" 29 ("Uniline")	0.63	38000	15.2	-	85
Polyester ("Uniline")	"	16000	15.1	-	78
Nylon ("Uniline")	"	16000	13.2	-	82
<u>BRAID</u>					
"Kevlar" 29 (med. pick)	9/16	34000	10.8	8	53
"Dacron" (med. pick)	"	16000	10.0	-	59
"Kevlar" 29 (long pick)	1/4	7100	1.3	5	92
Nylon (short pick)	"	2000	1.6	-	41
<u>WIRE ROPE CONSTRUCTION</u>					
"Kevlar" 29 (1x7)	1/8	2500		4	65
Galvanized (1x7)	"	2100	3.1	2.5	80
"Kevlar" 29 (7x7)	3/8	17000	4.7	-	62
Galvanized (7x7)	"	13100	23.6	-	71

*Conversion based on 375×10^3 psi for "Kevlar", 163×10^3 psi for polyester, 145×10^3 psi for nylon, 275×10^3 psi for steel - helix angle not considered.

FIGURE 6

AIRCRAFT APPLICATIONS

● "KEVLAR" 49

Interiors	Lower Weight
Floor Panels	Above + Good Impact
Cargo Liners	" " "
Fairings	" " "
Control Surfaces	" " "
Turbine Blade Containment	" " "
Doors and Access Panels	Above + Ease of Fabrication
Radomes	Radar Transparency
Drone Components	" "
Tooling for Graphite Parts	Low Thermal Expansion Coefficient
Spacecraft Antennas	" " " "

● "KEVLAR" 49/GRAPHITE

Helicopter Fuselages	Lower Cost Impact Resistance
" Rotor Blades	" " " "
" Drive Shafts	" " " "
Jet Engine Fan Blades	Impact Resistance

FIGURE 7
FILAMENT WOUND PRESSURE VESSELS

	<u>"Kevlar" 49</u>	<u>S-Glass</u>
Composite Density (lb/in ³)	0.044	0.039
Fiber Volume (%)	65	65
Composite Tensile Strength, 10 ³ psi	223,300	196,900
Specific Strength, 10 ⁶ in.	5.08	2.85
Relative Specific Strength	1.78	1.0
Composite Modulus, 10 ⁶ psi	13.2	8.8
Specific Modulus, 10 ⁸ in.	3.00	1.28
Relative Specific Modulus	2.34	1.0
Relative Cyclic Performance		
90% of Ultimate	10	1
60% of Ultimate	>3	1
Stress Rupture Life (hrs)		
80% of Ultimate	209	1
90% of Ultimate	1	Fails

FIGURE 8
SPORTING GOODS

	<u>"Kevlar"</u>	<u>"Kevlar"</u> <u>% Glass</u>	<u>"Kevlar"</u> <u>& Graphite</u>
Golf Clubs			✓
Canoes & Kayaks	✓	✓	
Archery Bows		✓	✓
Arrows		✓	
Hockey Sticks	W	✓	
Javelin			✓
Tennis Racket	W	✓	✓
Fishing Rod			✓
Snow Skis			✓
Sailboat Hulls		✓	
Paddles & Oars		✓	

W - With wood.

FIGURE 9

AIR SUPPORTED SHELTER MATERIAL

	<u>Nylon</u>	<u>"Kevlar" 29</u>
<u>FABRIC PROPERTIES</u>		
Weight, oz/yd ²	5.1	2.1
Tensile Strength Grab Method (WxF), lbs	380 x 375	215 x 230
Burst - Mullen, psi	800	930
<u>COATED* FABRIC PROPERTIES</u>		
Weight, oz/yd ²	15.0	11.3
Tensile Strength Grab Method (WxF), lbs	300 x 300	380 x 335
Tongue Tear Strength (WxF), lbs	20 x 20	20 x 25
Burst - Mullen, psi	840	900

*Hypalon® synthetic rubber

FIGURE 10

ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES OF "KEVLAR" 49 AND
GLASS FABRIC LAMINATES IN FR-4 RESIN SYSTEMS

	<u>"Kevlar" 49</u>	<u>Glass</u>
Dielectric Constant (ASTM D-150, 10 ⁶ Hz)		
Conditioned 72hr/23°C/50% RH	4.12	5.15
" 24hr/23°C/water	4.15	5.18
Dissipation Factor (ASTM D-150, 10 ⁶ Hz)		
Conditioned 72hr/23°C/50% RH	0.0239	0.0208
" 24hr/23°C/water	0.0247	0.0212
Dielectric Strength, volts/mil (ASTM D-149)		
Conditioned 72hr/23°C/50% RH + 24hr/23°C/water		
<u>Thickness, mils</u> - 29.4	959	-
70.6	663	-
75.7	-	654
35.7		785
Volume Resistivity, ohm/cm (ASTM D-257)	5 x 10 ¹⁵	2 x 10 ¹⁵
Surface Resistivity, ohm/square (ASTM D-257)	5 x 10 ¹⁵	3 x 10 ¹⁵
Arc Resistance, Seconds	125	123
<u>Samples</u> - Fabric Style	120	128
Plies	22	11
Thickness, Mils	68	75
v/o Fiber	50	46

Conditions: Tests at R.T. after samples had been conditioned at 73°F for 24 hours at 50% RH unless otherwise noted.

FIGURE 11.

RIGID CIRCUIT BOARD PROPERTIES

	<u>Paper/ Phenolic</u>	<u>Nonwoven "Kevlar" 49/ Epoxy</u>	<u>Woven Glass/Epoxy</u>
Fiber w/o	50	15	50
Resin w/o	50	85	50
Flex Strength, ksi	15	15	70
Impact Strength, ft-lb/in - MD	.7	3	10
Water Absorption, %	.5	.3	.1
Dielectric Constant	5.3	3.7	5.0
Dissipation Factor x 10 ³	30	28	17
Insulation Resistance, Megohms x 10 ⁻³ after 96 hrs at 90% RH	50	11,400	10,000
Adhesion of Copper, lb/in			
1-inch strips	8-10	10	10-12
1/8-inch strips	8-10	9	9-11
20 sec. at 500°F Solder Float	7-9	10	9-10
Dip Solder Test at 500°F, sec.	-	>60	>60

FIGURE 12

THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY

	Density lb/ft ³	BTU-ft			Burn			Smoke
		K = hr-ft ² °F			12-	Glow (sec.)	Time to 16% O.D.** (min.)	
		80°F	125°F	200°F	Seconds (in.)			Drip
● AIRCRAFT INSULATION BATTS								
<u>MATERIAL</u>								
"Kevlar" 49/Phenolic 80/20	0.80	0.274	0.306	0.38	1	No	No	14
"Kevlar" 49/Acrylic 80/20	0.80	0.255	0.290	0.36	1	No	No	10.5
Glass/Unknown Resin 80/20	1.20	0.290	0.390		← Unavailable →			
"Kevlar" 49/Phenolic 80/20	0.40	0.300	0.350	0.41*	1	No	No	11
"Kevlar" 49/Acrylic 80/20	0.40	0.305	0.355	0.45*	1	No	No	7.5
Glass/Unknown Resin 80/20	0.60	0.340	0.350	0.40	← Unavailable →			
FAA Specification 25.853	--	--	--	--	6	No	1	2
● FABRIC REINFORCED COMPOSITES***								
					<u>Thermal Conductivity</u>			
<u>Material</u>		<u>Heat Flux Direction</u>			<u>Cal-cm</u>	<u>BTU-ft</u>		
					<u>Sec cm²°C</u>	<u>hr ft²°F</u>		
"Kevlar" 49 S-120/Epoxy		Across Fabric Layers			4.95 x 10 ⁻⁴	0.124		
"Kevlar" 49 S-120/Epoxy		Parallel to Warp			21.0 x 10 ⁻⁴	0.525		
"Kevlar" 49 S-181/Epoxy		Across Fabric Layers			4.87 x 10 ⁻⁴	0.122		
Glass Fabric/Epoxy****		Across Fabric Layers			10.0 x 10 ⁻⁴	0.250		

*Measured at 212°F.

**O.D. - optical density.

***Nominal 50 v/o fiber.

****Materials Engineering, Materials Selector Issue, October 1969.